

1 Gate-to-Gate Life Cycle Assessment of Lithium-Ion Battery Recycling Pre-Treatment

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3 Anna Pražanová ^{a)}, Michael Fridrich ^{a, b)}, Jan Weinzettel ^{a, b)}, and Vaclav Knap ^{a)}

4 a) Department of Electrotechnology, Czech Technical University in Prague, Prague,
5 Czech Republic,

6 b) Charles University, Environment Centre Prague, Czech Republic,

7

8 * Corresponding author. E-mail address: anna.prazanova@cvut.cz (A. Pražanová).

9

10 Abstract

11 Recycling spent lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) represents a crucial step within end-of-life (EOL)
12 management, aiming to improve environmental sustainability and resource conservation.
13 However, due to the high application diversity of LIB cells and the recycling technology used,
14 little is known about the environmental and energy impacts. Hence, in terms of providing
15 comprehensive assessments, the distinctive and individual nature of the operations, applied
16 methodologies, the efficiency of the employed technology, or the final treatment of the
17 generated materials should be considered. This study presents a partial gate-to-gate life cycle
18 analysis (LCA) dedicated to the operation case study of the smaller-scaled recycling plant in
19 central Europe, specifically in the Czech Republic, focused on the recycling pre-treatment of
20 spent LIB systems from electric vehicles (EVs) and consumer electronics cells (CECs). The
21 study highlights the benefit of the recycling pre-treatment CECs technology, which
22 significantly reduced the monitored environmental impact categories (EICs), including climate
23 change, eutrophication, freshwater, resource use, minerals and metals. Moreover, the study
24 demonstrated that a high secondary use rate of the obtained materials is crucial to ensure the
25 environmental benefits, as the impacts of the avoided production of the replaced materials are

26 deducted. Metal reuse, including materials from packaging, connectors, and current collectors,
27 emerged as pivotal for secondary use and should be preferred over other battery component
28 materials.

29

30 **1. Introduction**

31 Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have become indispensable in modern technology due to
32 their high energy density, lightweight design, and rechargeability. They power various devices,
33 from portable consumer electronics to light or heavy means of transport, such as electric
34 vehicles (EVs) or renewable energy storage systems [1–3]. The LIBs integration within the
35 transport leads to a revolution in the automotive sector by providing a cleaner and more
36 sustainable alternative to traditional internal combustion engines [4,5]. Vehicles equipped with
37 LIBs offer reduced greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) and contribute to mitigating climate
38 change [5,6]. Nevertheless, the environmental benefit should be considered within the entire
39 lifespan of the product, process, or activity [7]. This includes not only the manufacturing and
40 use phases but also the disposal or end-of-life (EOL) stage [8].

41 Recycling holds significant benefits for both the environment and the economy [9–11].
42 Commonly used LIBs are rich in valuable metals in battery electrodes, such as cobalt, lithium,
43 manganese, and nickel, and other essential metals and minerals, including aluminum, copper,
44 graphite, or iron within the rest of battery components, such as battery collectors and casings
45 [9,12,13]. Considering the still-rising demand within a wide range of their application fields,
46 recycling LIBs is crucial for effective waste management. Moreover, recycling conservates
47 virgin material sources, minimizes the environmental impact associated with mining and
48 extraction, such as the production of GHGs or significant energy consumption, and contributes
49 to the circular economy by closing the loop on selected materials [14,15]. However, even the

50 recycling processes are energy-intensive, generate emissions into water and air, and pose the
51 risk of releasing toxic substances into the environment [10,16].

52 Life cycle analysis (LCA) is typically used to thoroughly assess the environmental
53 impacts of a product. LCA should ideally cover all stages of the product's life cycle, from raw
54 material extraction to disposal ("cradle-to-grave"), but it can also focus on specific life cycle
55 stages ("gate-to-gate") [8]. Evaluating specific life cycle phases is essential for understanding
56 the complexity and impact of comprehensive procedures. This assessment enables the
57 identification of opportunities for further optimization, ultimately reducing the overall
58 environmental impact of the monitored processes [7,8].

59 Very few LCAs addressing LIB recycling treatment have been documented in published
60 literature. Moreover, the works vary significantly in their aims, scope, level of detail, assumed
61 battery type, composition chemistry, and the employed assessment method. A comprehensive
62 analysis of the impacts of recycling using cradle-to-gate LCA, focusing on energy consumption
63 and greenhouse gas emissions of automotive LIBs, was provided by Dunn et al. [17]. Their
64 work covered the "closed loop" recycling by pyrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy, and direct
65 physical separation of the lithium manganese oxide (LMO) cathode and current collector
66 materials. According to their approach, the direct physical recycling of LMO, aluminum, and
67 copper could reduce energy consumption during material production by up to 48%. A similar
68 study was provided by Hendrickson et al. [18], who dealt with closed-loop pyrometallurgical
69 and hydrometallurgical processing of LMO. Their finding revealed that material recovery from
70 pyrometallurgy can mitigate environmental impacts associated with LIB production via a 6-
71 56% reduction in primary energy demand and a 23% reduction in GHG emissions compared to
72 virgin production. Further, the assessment of Elwert et al. [19] focused on hydrometallurgical
73 recycling of nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) LIBs, highlighted the environmental
74 benefits resulting from the recovery of the outer steel casing to a lesser degree, the cobalt and

75 nickel present in the cathode materials. Rajaeifar et al. [20] presented a comparative study of
76 different pyrometallurgical techniques. In contrast, Cusenza et al. [21] reported an evaluation
77 of recycling an LMO-NMC LIB pack using a combination of pyrometallurgical and
78 hydrometallurgical processes.

79 However, a significant knowledge gap remains in the environmental assessment of the
80 initial stage of recycling LIBs, known as recycling pre-treatment [9,22,23]. This phase
81 encompasses battery discharging, disassembly, crushing, rough material separation, and
82 removing organic components through thermal treatment. The treatment product, known as
83 black mass, is a finely ground mixture of diverse materials sourced from battery components,
84 notably containing valuable metals [11]. Black mass is subsequently processed in specialized
85 plants, primarily focused on direct material recovery [9,11,24,25].

86 This paper aims to fill this gap by presenting a gate-to-gate LCA focusing on the
87 operation of a pilot recycling plant, particularly emphasizing the pre-treatment of LIB systems
88 sourced from EVs and consumer electronics cells (CECs). The provided case study, which was
89 for a demonstration considered in the conditions of the Czech Republic, assesses plant operation
90 on a single shift basis for 252 days annually and processing 500 tonnes of EV battery systems
91 and an additional 48 tonnes of CECs yearly. The study examines representatives from the most
92 important battery types: NMC technology, prevalent in EVs, alongside commonly used CEC
93 types like LMO, lithium iron phosphate (LFP), and lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide
94 (NCA). Essential indicators derived from the LCA phase, including climate change,
95 eutrophication, freshwater use, resource use, minerals and metals, are utilized for assessment.
96 The work highlights the advantageous impact of recycling pre-treatment for both LIB cell types,
97 with CECs demonstrating superior treatment outcomes compared to EV cells. Moreover, the
98 study delineates the influence of technology efficiency and secondary usage rate on
99 environmental indicators, underscoring the importance of optimal technological application and

100 secondary material utilization. Lack of secondary material utilization exacerbates
101 environmental impacts, even with high-quality technology, accentuating the imperative
102 of comprehensive waste management practices. Metal reuse emerges as a pivotal strategy,
103 warranting prioritization over other battery components to mitigate environmental degradation
104 effectively.

105

106 **2. Materials and methods**

107 **2.1 Goal, scope, and assumptions**

108 LCA is a standardized and broadly embraced methodology used to compile and evaluate the
109 potential environmental impacts associated with a product, process, or service. It typically
110 examines the entire life cycle, from raw material extraction (cradle) to disposal (grave), a
111 process known as "cradle-to-grave analysis." However, partial LCA studies, referred to as
112 "gate-to-gate," focus on specific process stages to provide a detailed evaluation, emphasizing
113 either benefits or drawbacks [8]. This study aimed to evaluate the environmental impacts of
114 LIB recycling pre-treatment by providing the gate-to-gate LCA. Moreover, it assumes recycled
115 secondary materials to reduce the need for primary materials, which results in positive
116 environmental impacts due to "avoided production".

117 The study evaluates the operation case of a recycling plant in central Europe, specifically
118 in the Czech Republic, which is dedicated to the recycling pre-treatment of spent LIB systems
119 from electric vehicles (EVs) and consumer electronics cells (CECs). A schematic illustration of
120 the evaluated five-step recycling pre-treatment, with characterized process inputs and outputs,
121 is shown in Figure 1 (a). The whole process starts with a deep discharge step, which is essential
122 for further safe and promising processing [9,26]. For EV technology, the electric active
123 discharging procedures are typically preferred [11]. Thus, for the case of EV battery systems
124 (packs), a suitable battery discharge system with reduced energy consumption and high

125 effectivity with a recovery energy capability of up to 96% is used. Within the CECs treatment,
126 electrochemical discharge in 10 wt. % sodium chloride (NaCl) and water solution, as the
127 favourable discharging procedure, is applied [27,28]. The battery packs are manually
128 disassembled using only small power tools at the battery module level due to the high
129 complexity and wide variety of treated systems. The next step involves crushing either battery
130 cells or entire battery units, facilitating the separation of their materials [9,11]. The modules are
131 subsequently crushed in a two-step procedure using a double-shaft rubber recycling crusher and
132 a rotor impact mill. In this stage, only volatile solvents or particulate matter are emitted and
133 subsequently removed via ventilation systems. The scope of this study does not cover their
134 more detailed processing or reusing. Crushing CECs is done likewise. During the
135 electrochemical discharging, volatile solvents and electrolyte are released into the solution. This
136 wastewater is disposed of as hazardous waste. The treated cells are rinsed with water and
137 crushed using the same process steps as in the EV route. The final product of this line is black
138 mass, i.e., a finely ground mix of fractions of battery components [11], which has been treated
139 with selected processes (separation and thermal treatment) to remove plastics, binders,
140 conductive additives, electrolyte residues, or other materials such as current collector metals
141 (copper and aluminum), graphite from anode layers or casing materials (iron and steel).

142

143 **Figure 1.** (a) Process scheme of recycling pre-treatment routes for spent lithium-ion batteries
 144 from electric vehicles and consumer electronics; (b) the energy mix composition for analysed
 145 scenarios 2022 and 2030 [29]; (c) life cycle of lithium-ion battery with a highlighted study
 146 scope (in red), related to gate-to-gate LCA of recycling pre-treatment.

147

148 The assessment was conducted for a case study of a smaller-scaled pilot recycling line,
 149 which handles approximately one-third of the processing capacity compared to the current

150 operations in central Europe [30]. Thus, single-shift operation (8 working hours) for 252 days
151 per year was considered. The processing of EV battery systems and CECs in the recycling plant
152 is not done simultaneously. EV battery packs are processed for 240 days and CECs for 12 days
153 (i.e., once a month) per year. It was assumed that one battery pack weighs between 400-420 kg,
154 and 5 of these systems are processed during the shift, with a total annual processing of 500
155 tonnes. For CECs, 4 tons per shift with a total processing of 48 tonnes per year was considered.
156 Due to the advantages of nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) technology, which is one of
157 the leading chemical types of EV LIB today, the processing of EV battery systems of this type
158 was considered. In the case of CECs, the processing of cells based on lithium manganese oxide
159 (LMO), lithium iron phosphate (LFP), and lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide (NCA),
160 all in the same ratio, i.e., 16 tonnes of batteries of each type per year, was determined. The
161 material proportion and mass of treated individual battery components are specified in Table 1.
162

Cell type	EV cells		Consumer electronics cells (CECs)						
	NMC	Total (tonnes)	LMO		LFP		NCA		Total (tonnes)
Battery component	wt. %		wt. %	Total (tonnes)	wt. %	Total (tonnes)	wt. %	total (tonnes)	
Cathode	40	200	24	3.84	28	4.48	25	4.00	12.32
Al foils	15	75	17	2.72	19	3.04	15	2.40	8.16
Active materials	25	125	7	1.12	9	1.44	10	1.60	4.16
Anode	24	120	16	2.56	19	3.04	17	2.72	8.32
Cu foils	12	60	8	1.28	9	1.44	8	1.28	4.00
Graphite	12	60	8	1.28	10	1.6	9	1.44	4.32
Plastics	5	25	5	0.80	5	0.8	5	0.80	2.40

Metals	14	70	15	2.40	13	2.08	14	2.24	6.72
Binders	7	35	4	0.64	2	0.32	4	0.64	1.60
Electrolyte	10	50	36	5.76	33	5.28	35	5.60	16.64
Total	100	500	100	16	100	16	100	16	48

163

164 **Table 1.** The material proportion and mass of treated lithium-ion battery components [9,31–
165 33]. The mass of cathode active materials corresponds to the maximal amounts of possibly
166 obtained black mass in its highest quality.

167

168 In the assessed case, the recycling hall of the plant spans an area of 200 m²,
169 complemented by a 100 m² battery warehouse. The evaluation encompasses energy
170 consumption for heating, air conditioning, security monitoring, and additional ventilation
171 during electrochemical discharge or battery unit crushing. Furthermore, detailed information
172 regarding the energy consumption of individual recycling preparation or revision processes
173 is provided in the Supplementary materials.

174

175 **2.2 Evaluated scenario and sensitivity analysis**

176 This study evaluates the plant's operation dedicated to recycling pre-treatment of spent
177 LIBs in their EV battery packs, and CECs type was conducted based on an implementation
178 scenario (Scenario 2022) utilizing the average energy mix data of the Czech Republic for 2022.
179 Additionally, to illustrate the impact of changes in the energy mix composition over time,
180 Scenario 2022 was compared to the predicted energy mix composition for 2030 (Scenario
181 2030). The composition of the energy mix in 2022 relied on data from the Czech electricity and
182 gas market operator (OTE) database [34]. Predictions for the 2030 energy mix were drawn from
183 the "Resource Adequacy Assessment of the Electrical Grid of the Czech Republic until 2040"

184 (MAF CZ 2022) [29]. The composition of considered energy mixes is shown in Figure 1 (b).
185 Both case studies assumed ~100% efficiency for the recycling technology and a ~100% share
186 of secondary use for the obtained materials. The materials were separated with ~100%
187 efficiency, ensuring the resulting black mass achieved the highest possible quality. Detailed
188 quantities of the output materials are provided in Table 1. Furthermore, the potential for
189 secondary use was maximized, aligning with the primary objective of recycling. In sensitivity
190 analyses, materials not obtained as secondary materials (and therefore have no negative
191 environmental impacts) represent the Cut-Off modeling approach.

192 Sensitivity analysis 1 (SA1) is dedicated to Scenario 2022 and describes the effects
193 of the implemented technology efficiency, which directly impacts the quality of the obtained
194 materials. In this case, a ~100% secondary use of the recovered materials was assumed.
195 The efficiency of the process is determined by the percentage of obtained materials, according
196 to their materials type, including electrolyte, plastics, binders, graphite, metals, and Al & Cu
197 foils within the material flows of the recycling pre-treatment operation, as illustrated in Table
198 2. Detailed data are provided in Supplementary materials.

199 Sensitivity analysis 2 (SA2) is focused on assessing the secondary use effect in Scenario
200 2022. The evaluation considers the highest quality black mass product (achieved through
201 ~100% efficiency of the implemented technology), and the secondary usage shares for selected
202 material groups are shown in Table 2.

203 In an ideal scenario, materials such as Al and copper Cu foils, metals, graphite, and
204 plastics are considered secondary materials, which can be recycled and reused. However,
205 electrolytes are typically only partially treated through wastewater or incinerated in kilns.
206 Binders, on the other hand, are always directed to landfills. Furthermore, if secondary materials
207 are not recycled, they end up in landfills. Within the provided sensitivity analysis, the scenarios
208 are severely idealistic. While the energy mix used to power the recycling pre-treatment, line

209 improves in time (emissions get lower), the environmental footprint of avoided products stays
 210 the same. This leads to a higher positive impact of battery recycling on the environment.

211 The input data of this evaluation are given in Supplementary materials.

212

Sensitivity analysis parameter	Material category	SA1 variants (based on Scenario 2022)				
		A	B	C	D	Scenario 2022
Technology efficiency	Electrolyte	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %
	Plastics, binders	0 %				
	Graphite	0 %				
	Metals	80 %	80 %	80 %		
	Al & Cu foils			80 %		
Sensitivity analysis parameter	Material category	SA2 variants (based on Scenario 2022)				
		X	Y	Z	Scenario 2022	
Secondary usage	Electrolyte	0 %	0 %	50 %	100 %	
	Plastics, binders					
	Graphite					
	Metals		100 %			
	Al & Cu foils					

213

214 **Table 2.** The assumptions for sensitivity analyses for the evaluation of scenario recycling pre-
 215 treatment operation for spent lithium-ion batteries.

216

217

218 **2.3 Life cycle assessment approach**

219 This study provides a partial gate-to-gate LCA for the selected recycling pre-treatment
220 processes for spent LIBs, conducted via the 9.5.0.0 version of SimaPro LCA modeling software
221 using the Ecoinvent 3.9. database with a Cut-Off approach and Environmental Footprint 3.1
222 (EF 3.1) life cycle impact assessment method. The scope of this study within the whole LIB
223 life cycle is highlighted in red and shown in Figure 1(c).

224 The environmental impact categories (EICs) typically vary depending on the assessment
225 context and the study's specific goals. However, some commonly recognized EICs include
226 climate change, resource depletion, water pollution, air pollution, ecotoxicity, land use, and
227 waste generation. In terms of this study, three main EICs were determined. They cover climate
228 change, eutrophication, freshwater, resource use, minerals and metals. These EICs were chosen
229 due to their close relation to the industry's impact and based on normalized results [8].

230 The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) characterization model is the
231 basis for evaluating the impacts of climate change. This model provides characterization
232 factors, which are quantified as the Global Warming Potential over a 100-year time frame
233 (GWP100), measured in kilograms of carbon dioxide equivalent (kg CO₂ eq.) per kilogram of
234 emission. The geographic scope of this indicator is at a global scale. The Global Warming
235 Potential (GWP) data reported in the IPCC are exclusively associated with emissions to air. To
236 align these values with the classifications used in the ILCD (International Life Cycle Data
237 system) and EF (Environmental Footprint) frameworks, they were distributed across different
238 emission compartments, such as: emissions to the lower stratosphere and upper troposphere,
239 emissions to non-urban air or from high stacks, emissions to urban air close to the
240 ground [8,35,36].

241 Eutrophication, freshwater EIC measures the degree to which freshwater ecosystems
242 become overly enriched with nutrients, stemming from emissions of compounds containing

243 phosphorus. Known as eutrophication or nitrification, this process encompasses all effects
244 linked to the excessive presence of macronutrients in the environment, originating from nutrient
245 emissions to air, water, and soil. Additionally, it represents the expression of the degree to
246 which the emitted nutrients reach the freshwater end compartment (phosphorus is considered a
247 limiting factor in freshwater) [37].

248 Resource use, minerals and metals EIC focuses on the consumption of natural non-fossil
249 resources, specifically minerals and metals. It addresses the protection of human welfare,
250 health, and ecosystem health. The indicator is associated with the extraction of minerals and
251 fossil fuels as inputs into various systems. The Abiotic Depletion Factor (ADF) calculates the
252 impact of each mineral and fossil fuel extraction, expressed in kilograms of antimony
253 equivalents (Sb eq.), considering reserve concentrations and the rate of depletion. This
254 indicator's applicability is global, encompassing the entire planet [8,35,38].

255 Due to the very different recycling pre-treatment processing methods of EV battery
256 systems and CECs, as well as the different chemical composition of the individual cells, the
257 unit in which environmental impacts were assessed was standardized to one metric tonne of
258 product, specifically black mass. This functional unit brings an understandable and clear
259 comparison between the selected recycling pre-treatment pathways. Alternatively, the unit of
260 evaluation could have been a tonne or a pack of recycled batteries. Details of the evaluation,
261 using one metric tonne of waste batteries intended for recycling as the functional unit, are
262 provided in the Supplementary materials of this work.

263

264

265

266

267 **3. Results and discussion**

268 This study evaluates the environmental impacts of recycling pre-treatment of spent LIBs
269 via selected EICs. A negative value indicates that the environmental impacts of pre-treatment
270 are lower than the environmental impacts of the primary production of the output recycled
271 materials.

272

273 **3.1 Scenario 2022 and 2030 comparison**

274 The comprehensive assessment of this study included determining the total annual EIC
275 characterization for selected operation scenarios and comparing the difference between the
276 energy mix in 2022 and 2030. These impacts are summarized and provided in the
277 Supplementary materials of this work.

278 The environment is significantly affected by recycling pre-treatment of spent LIBs.
279 According to this performed study, a reduction or mitigation of selected impacts is observed
280 within all monitored EICs. However, other sub-parts of the study, including the sensitivity
281 analyses, are dedicated to a standardized comparison with the assistance of a functional unit
282 (one metric tonne of black mass). The comparison of case study scenarios modeled based on
283 different energy mixes for 2022 and 2030, as depicted in Figure 2.

284

285 **Figure 2.** Comparing scenarios regarding varied energy mix compositions in both 2022 and
 286 2030. Results reflect the standardized comparison with the assistance of a functional unit (one
 287 metric tonne of black mass).

288

289 The comparison reveals a higher reduction of environmental impacts when recycling
 290 CECs over EV cells. When assessed based on the energy mix of 2022, the results of EV cells
 291 were only 32.90% for climate change, 42.99% for eutrophication, freshwater, and 50.09% for
 292 resource use, minerals and metals, compared to CECs. The significant differences in resource
 293 use, minerals and metals impact category between CECs and EV cells primarily stem from
 294 variations in the ratios of internal materials, such as cathode active materials. This variation is
 295 a key contributor to the negative environmental impacts associated with recycling lithium-ion
 296 batteries (LIBs). Proper processing of CECs is essential for environmental sustainability,
 297 underscoring the significance of addressing this type of waste LIBs in recycling pre-treatment
 298 initiatives.

299 In addition, while the energy mixes in this comparison vary, the production of avoided
 300 products (such as aluminum and copper) remains constant across the two scenarios. Upon

301 comparison, it becomes evident that the energy mix exerts a significant impact (>20%)
302 on eutrophication and freshwater EIC, a moderate effect (<17%) on climate change EIC, and a
303 nearly negligible influence (<1%) on the resource use, minerals and metals EIC. Overall, the
304 2030 scenario demonstrates a notable increase in environmental benefits concerning the former
305 two categories. This change is primarily attributed to the diminishing reliance on coal-fired
306 power plants, which accounted for nearly half of the Czech Republic's energy mix in 2022.
307 Nevertheless, their usage is expected to decrease to less than a third by 2030. Conversely,
308 regarding its influence on resource use, minerals and metals, the benefits show a decline and
309 stagnation, with a marginal change of 0.20% observed for both compared to treated battery cell
310 technologies.

311

312 **3.1.1 A detailed breakdown within Scenario 2022**

313 To provide a thorough depiction of the evaluation of the influence and characteristics of
314 the output product, a detailed breakdown was devised for Scenario 2022, as illustrated in Figure
315 3. This breakdown encompasses the processing of output materials in various impact categories,
316 including the “recycling line, waste binders, and electrolyte (which also incorporates electricity
317 flows in plant operation), wastewater treatment, secondary plastic parts, secondary iron and
318 steel, secondary aluminum, secondary copper, and secondary graphite”; through their impacts
319 and total impacts within selected EICs were determined.

320 The analysed EICs directly reflect the nature of further processing of the selected
321 materials in generated output categories. During disposal (category "recycling line, waste
322 binders, and electrolyte; wastewater treatment"), a positive effect was determined for all EICs.
323 Conversely, the reuse of materials, which covers the "secondary" labeled categories, disposes
324 of negative values and, therefore, reduces overall impacts. In this study, no wastewater
325 processing in the context of EV battery unit treatment was considered, thus, no/zero impact

326 within all selected EICs was observed. The details of the pre-treatment steps layout are provided
327 in Figure 1(a).

328 The categories "secondary copper" and "secondary aluminum" significantly contribute
329 to the breakdown, as it is assumed that they will replace primary production, which potential
330 impacts are deducted. This is most influenced by these metals assumed 100 % recovery rate.
331 Within the resource use, minerals and metals EIC, the influence of aluminum is minimal
332 because aluminum is not considered a scarce material. On the other hand, the production of
333 aluminum, which demands high energy, has a major impact on climate change. In comparison,
334 copper has a more significant effect on metal depletion.

335

336 **Figure 3.** A detailed breakdown into generated output EICs within Scenario 2022, a) climate
 337 change, b) eutrophication, freshwater, and c) resource use, minerals and metals.

338 **3.2 Sensitivity analysis**

339 Two different sensitivity analyses are provided in this study. SA1 presents the impact
340 effect of technology efficiency, while SA2 focuses on the impact of secondary material usage
341 via selected EICs. For clarity, the study results are classified based on the battery cell type,
342 considering the EV cells and CECs, in Figures (a) and (b), respectively. The compared variants
343 are arranged from the least to the most efficient technology or secondary material usage and
344 listed alphabetically. During the evaluation of the analysis results, the variant showing the most
345 significant environmental benefit (the most negative EIC value) was consistently regarded as
346 the baseline, representing 100%. All other variants were evaluated with this baseline to gauge
347 their impact and alterations. Additional analysis details are described in Table 2.

348

349 **3.2.1 Technology efficiency impact**

350 The impacts of all monitored EICs for both battery technologies are contingent upon the
351 effectiveness of the technology employed. All analysed scenarios lead to negative impacts;
352 nevertheless, as the efficiency of the technology decreases, so does the ability to reduce or
353 mitigate environmental impacts. The results of SA1 are illustrated in detail in Figure 4.

354

355 **Figure 4.** Sensitivity analysis 1 results describing the effect of efficiency of implemented
 356 technology for (a) consumer electronics cells and (b) electric vehicle cells. Presented results
 357 reflect the standardized comparison with the assistance of a functional unit (one metric tonne
 358 of black mass).

359 Within the analysis of both battery types, a difference was noted between the rate of
 360 change of EICs depending on the efficiency of the technology used. In the case of EV batteries,

361 the slightest change of all categories was characterized between variants C and D. This change,
362 based only on a 20% increase in the efficiency of the technology from 80 to 100% for metals
363 recycling, ranged from 6.33% for climate change, 5.41% for eutrophication, freshwater and
364 5.55% for resource use, minerals and metals. Compared with CECs, the changes were as
365 follows: 8.96% for climate change, 8.18% for eutrophication, freshwater, and 8.54% for
366 resource use, minerals and metals. The most significant change was achieved when the
367 efficiency of Al and Cu foil recycling technology was increased to 100%, the difference
368 between variants D and "energy mix 2022", where the change reached up to 35.94% for climate
369 change, 38.82% for eutrophication, freshwater and 34.20% for resource use, minerals and
370 metals.

371 For CECs, on the other hand, the slightest difference was recorded within the framework
372 of changes to variants A and B, i.e., thorough separation and processing of plastics and binders.
373 Since the same proportion of plastics was considered for both EV and CEC technology, this
374 change is primarily caused by the different amounts of binders in the individual cells. This
375 change, characterized by a 100% increase in the efficiency of plastics and binders processing
376 (recycling and landfilling, respectively), ranged from 6.28% for climate change, 5.92% for
377 eutrophication, freshwater, and 6.68% for resource use, minerals and metals. Compared with
378 EV technology, the changes were as follows: 10.75% for climate change, 8.94% for
379 eutrophication, freshwater, and 9.31% for resource use, minerals and metals. The most
380 significant change was also achieved between variants D and "energy mix 2022", where the
381 change was around 50%, i.e., 50.73% for climate change, 53.01% for eutrophication, freshwater
382 and 49.57% for resource use, minerals and metals.

383 In both recycling pre-treatment pathways, a moderate difference in change was noted
384 between variants B and C. The increase in technology efficiency, specifically achieving 100%
385 graphite processing, yielded similar outcomes for both technologies. This increase ranged

386 between 15-18%, including 18.26% for climate change, 15.79% for eutrophication, freshwater,
387 16.03% for resource use, minerals and metals for EV cells, and 17.31% for climate change,
388 15.04% for eutrophication, freshwater, and 14.82% for resource use, minerals and metals for
389 CECs.

390 In the SA1 results, it's important to emphasize that ~100% of the obtained materials are
391 repurposed. Either recycled as secondary materials or landfilled. With appropriate secondary
392 treatment, LIB recycling pre-treatment processing is highly beneficial, resulting in reduced
393 impacts on categories such as climate change, eutrophication, freshwater, and resource use,
394 minerals and metals. Based on the results, the effective processing and separation of metallic
395 materials, especially current collectors of batteries (Al & Cu foils), has the most crucial role.
396 The change in the processing efficiency of plastics and binders had a negligible effect on all
397 monitored EICs.

398

399 **3.1.2 Secondary material usage impact**

400 When comparing the results of SA2, it becomes evident that the secondary use method
401 serves as a crucial processing parameter during recycling pre-treatment. It has significantly
402 influenced the extent and characteristics of its impact, as illustrated in Figure 5.

403 The most minor difference between variants occurred for EV cells and CECs when
404 comparing variant Y to "energy mix 2022". This comparison involved 100% secondary use of
405 cell metals, including battery packaging, contacts, and Al and Cu current collectors, against the
406 complete utilization (recycling as secondary materials) of all cell materials represented by
407 "energy mix 2022". For EV cells, this difference amounted to 17.53% for climate change,
408 4.56% for eutrophication, freshwater, and only 0.20% for resource use, minerals and metals.
409 Similarly, for CECs, the difference was 13.13% for climate change, 4.31% for eutrophication,

410 freshwater, and merely 0.24% for resource use, minerals and metals. These results underscore
411 the significance of secondary metal use in achieving high environmental benefits.

412 The importance of processing metal parts is also emphasized, considering the results of
413 variant Z, which includes 50% reuse of obtained materials. Although the resulting contribution
414 to reducing the impact of EICs is minor, it is still negative and leads to overall environmental
415 benefits. When compared with the variant of complete processing "energy mix 2022", it
416 achieves 32.78% for climate change, 32.85% for eutrophication, freshwater, and 49.94% for
417 resource use, minerals and metals for EV cells and 35.6% for climate change, 32.92% for
418 eutrophication, freshwater, and 49.67% for resource use, minerals and metals.

419 The evaluation presents the importance of secondary use, highlighted via variant X,
420 which includes no secondary processing of the obtained materials. This variant, as the only one
421 of all compared, does not reduce, but on the contrary, increases the environmental impact in all
422 monitored categories. If the materials are not processed, there is a deterioration of climate
423 change by up to 34.44% for EV cells, 28.80% for CECs, a worsening of the impacts of
424 eutrophication, freshwater by 34.31% for EV cells, 34.17 for CECs. Resource depletion
425 or environmental degradation within resource use, minerals and metals category are minimal:
426 0.20% for EV cells and 0.24% for CECs.

428

429 **Figure 5.** Sensitivity analysis 2 results address the effect of the secondary material impact usage
 430 for (a) consumer electronics cells and (b) electric vehicle cells. Presented results reflect the
 431 standardized comparison with the assistance of a functional unit (one metric tonne of black
 432 mass).

433

434 **3.2.3 Sensitivity analysis results**

435 When comparing the results obtained from both SA1 and SA2 analyses, secondary use
436 is a crucial factor in the recycling preparation and waste treatment of LIBs, regardless of the
437 recycled type of batteries (EV cells or CECs). Even with the low efficiency of the technology
438 used, i.e., low-quality separation of materials and a reduction in the amount of the obtained
439 share, but 100% reuse of recovered materials, the results of the study were environmentally
440 favourable, reducing the influence of individual EICs in the range from 17 to 64%. Conversely,
441 even with the use of high-quality technology, when up to 100% of all battery materials would
442 be recovered, it has been proven that neglecting the secondary use of the obtained materials
443 will not eliminate environmental effects but instead produce them, up to 35% on a scale defined
444 based on the maximum benefit effect ("energy efficiency 2022" variant). From the view of
445 secondary use, the key is reusing all metal parts of batteries, i.e., battery cases, contacts, or
446 current collector materials.

447

448 **4. Conclusion**

449 Adopting advanced and sustainable waste treatment methods in the contemporary EOL
450 management approach of LIB processing is paramount. Among these methods, recycling is
451 crucial to converting spent components such as electrodes, current collectors, terminals,
452 contacts, and packaging into reusable or new materials. This technique can significantly
453 contribute to environmental sustainability and ecological impact reduction, which will correlate
454 with legislation aims. Given the dynamic nature of the battery field, characterized by the novelty
455 of used technologies, diverse battery types, and evolving processing techniques, it is imperative
456 to scrutinize each approach thoroughly, considering even the most minor details.

457 Hence, this study presents a partial gate-to-gate LCA devoted to the operational case
458 study of the smaller-scaled pilot recycling plant in the Czech Republic, focused on the recycling

459 pre-treatment of spent LIB systems from EVs and CECs. The plant operates a single shift daily
460 (8 working hours) for 252 days per year, processing 500 tonnes of EV and 48 tonnes of CECs
461 battery systems annually. Additionally, the study focuses on NMC technology, the predominant
462 chemistry used in current EVs, and includes the commonly used types of CECs: LMO, LFP,
463 and NCA. The primary indicators for this work were selected based on their close relation
464 to the industry's impact, derived from the normalized results. These EICs, including climate
465 change, eutrophication, freshwater, and resource use, minerals and metals, were used as primary
466 indicators for this work.

467 The research highlights the benefits of recycling pre-treatment for both LIB cell types.
468 Moreover, it reveals a notable advantage in treating CECs compared to EV cells. Due to the
469 generally lower proportion of precious metals in the CECs' active cathode materials, this cell
470 type can be considered secondary regarding preferences in EOL LIB processing. However, in
471 terms of sustainability evaluation, it is necessary to consider all recycling steps or processing
472 phases. In the current situation, where many recycling lines are focused only on obtaining black
473 mass as their final output, it is impossible to assess the benefits of recycling based on the
474 composition and black mass treatment. Commonly, it is necessary to emphasize the benefits of
475 individual process phases, the impacts of obtaining material treatment, and implementation
476 procedures. Thus, integrating suitable recycling pre-treatment practices for all LIB types,
477 including the CECs, plays a pivotal role in highly sustainable EOL treatment and should be
478 mandated as a necessary step in waste management.

479 Moreover, this study describes the effect of technology level and secondary usage rate
480 on selected EICs. With the decreasing technology efficiency, the ability to avoid environmental
481 impacts is also reduced. Even at the lowest efficiency level of the technology, the effect
482 of recycling preprocessing was still beneficial. However, the rate of secondary utilization of the
483 acquired materials holds significant environmental implications. The lack of secondary material

484 utilization led to deterioration and increased environmental impact across all monitored
485 categories, even with high-quality technology, where up to ~100% of all battery materials could
486 be separated. Metal reuse, encompassing materials from packaging, connectors, and current
487 collectors, emerged as crucial, with negligible differences noted among the compared variants,
488 and thus should be prioritized over other battery component materials. These findings are
489 consistent with the work by Mohr et al. [39], who evaluated the recycling of LIBs and
490 highlighted the significant environmental benefits of recovering secondary aluminum and
491 copper, particularly in terms of impact on climate change and resource use.

492 The present study represents a pivotal analysis of the LIB recycling pre-treatment, which
493 underscores the significance of secondary material utilization and elucidates the requisite steps
494 in pre-treatment. To comprehensively evaluate the EOL phase of LIBs, additional research is
495 warranted to explore the processing of resultant materials, notably the black mass, employing
496 widely adopted industrial recycling methodologies such as pyrometallurgy or hydrometallurgy,
497 leading to valuable metals recovery. Additionally, it is recommended that additional inquiries
498 be made into alternative recycling methodologies, notably direct recycling, due to their
499 significant potential for enhancing sustainability.

500

501 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

502 **Anna Pražanová:** Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization, Writing – Original draft,
503 Project administration.

504 **Michael Fridrich:** Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Investigation.

505 **Jan Winzettel:** Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing.

506 **Vaclav Knap:** Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing, Funding acquisition, Project
507 administration.

508

509 **Declaration of competing interest**

510 All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

511

512 **Data availability**

513 Data will be made available on request.

514

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521

522 **Supplementary data**

523 Supplementary data to this article can be found online at XXX.

524

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